

Local Government in South Africa

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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1. The System of Local Government in South Africa

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Types of Local Governments

South Africa has a multilevel system of government organised at national, provincial and local level. There are nine provincial governments while the local sphere of government is constituted by 257 municipalities. The 1996 Constitution of South Africa recognises three categories of municipalities – Category A, B and C.¹ Metropolitan municipalities (Category A) have exclusive municipal executive and legislative authority in their respective areas of jurisdiction. Local municipalities (Category B), which currently total 205, share their municipal executive and legislative authority with district municipalities (Category C) within the relevant area they fall. District municipalities exercise their municipal executive and legislative authority in an area that covers more than one local municipality. These umbrella municipalities (currently 44) were established, among other reasons, to provide support and maximise on economies of scale in areas where there are low capacity municipalities. At policy level, the three broad categories of municipalities (A, B and C) are further broken down into seven sub-categories namely:

- A - metropolitan municipalities;
- B1 - secondary cities, local municipalities with the largest budgets;
- B2 - local municipalities with a large town as core;
- B3 - local municipalities with small towns, with relatively small population and significant proportion of urban population but with no large town as core;
- B4 - local municipalities which are mainly rural with communal tenure and with, at most, one or two small towns in their area;
- C1 - district municipalities which are not water services authorities; and
- C2 - district municipalities which are water services authorities.

National departments often make use of this sub-classification when dealing with municipalities.

The Constitution assigns to local government service delivery responsibilities and a development mandate. It equips local government with a variety of powers – legislative (the power to adopt by-laws), executive, fiscal, budget and administrative powers - to enable the delivery of these responsibilities and obligations. The functional areas of local government are enumerated in Schedule 4 (part B) and Schedule 5 (part B) of the Constitution. These schedules

¹ See Sec 155(1) of the Constitution.

list matters, such as water supply, and electricity reticulation, land use planning, municipal health, local roads, and refuse removal. The principles of subsidiarity and assignment recognised in the Constitution provide opportunities for municipalities to exercise additional functions.

Legal Status of Local Governments

Unlike in many countries, local government is recognised in the Constitution of South Africa as a sphere of government.² Thus, the existence of the institution of local government is not dependent on the goodwill of the national and provincial governments. This security of existence is extended to individual municipalities which may not be arbitrarily abolished or merged. Such abolishment or merger can only take place in terms of law and subject to oversight procedures that include the role of an independent body, the Municipal Demarcation Board.

The autonomy of municipalities is constitutionally recognised and can be enforced through the courts. Municipalities have a right to govern their respective areas and this right is only limited by the Constitution. The national and provincial governments may, however, regulate the exercise of this right but subject to limitations imposed by the Constitution. For instance, such regulation mainly takes the form of framework legislation that may not go to the 'core' of municipal functions as that is reserved for the legislative authority of municipal councils. National and provincial governments are further prohibited from impeding or compromising a municipality's ability to exercise this right whether by legislative or other means (Section 151(4) of the Constitution). Thus, it can be observed that unlike in many other countries, the Constitution of South Africa entrenches the existence and autonomy of local government that is jealously guarded by the courts in practice.

(A) Symmetry of the Local Government System

As explained above, there are three categories of municipalities in South Africa – metropolitan, local and district. The Constitution allocates to all metropolitan municipalities equal powers and functions. As opposed to metropolitan municipalities that have exclusive executive and legislative authority in their areas of jurisdiction, legislation and policy defines the division of responsibilities between district and local municipalities. As stated above, within the category of district municipalities there are those that have been designated as water services authorities and those that are not.

² See Sec 40(1) of the Constitution.

The Constitution entrenches the principles of subsidiarity and assignment which if implemented can also result in municipalities within and across categories exercising varying powers. Section 156(4) of the Constitution requires the national and provincial governments to assign to a municipality any of their functions if the function can ‘most effectively be administered locally and the municipality has the capacity to administer it’. This provision is being implemented with respect to some functional areas of the national and provincial governments. For example, metropolitan municipalities, which tend to have significant capacity, are already involved in the delivery of housing even though it is a national and provincial competence. Thus, there is a fair degree of asymmetry in the South African system of local government.

However, the Constitution does not explicitly state that the asymmetry at local level is strictly there to respond to the urban-rural distinction. In practice, nonetheless, district municipalities generally operate in rural and semi-rural areas while metropolitan municipalities and secondary cities (B1) govern in mostly urban areas. Thus, it can be concluded that the local government system is designed in such a way that enables it to respond or adjust to the urban-rural interplay, among other differences present at the local level.

Political and Social Context in South Africa

The ushering of a democratic era in 1994 brought hope to a country that had been ravaged by years of apartheid. Under apartheid, the state, economy and society were organised strictly on the basis of race.³ The system benefited whites while the majority black population, as well as the minority Indian/Asian and coloured minority groups, were marginalised, deprived of equal economic opportunities and political representation to a different degree, and the former relegated to third class citizens. Since coming to power in 1994, under the leadership of Nelson Mandela, the majority led government of the African National Congress (ANC) has been confronted with a major challenge of undoing or redressing the injustices and legacy of apartheid. A variety of transformation interventions have been adopted in line with the demands of one of the most transformative constitutions in the world, the 1996 Constitution.

These interventions have recorded successes in some areas while failures are common in a number of areas, such as spatial transformation, with apartheid spatial landscape largely remaining intact 27 years after the end of apartheid.⁴ Corruption and skills deficit, among other problems, continue to undermine the capability of the state to meet its obligation and development priorities at all levels of government.⁵ The slow growth of one of Africa’s largest

³ See Nico Steytler and Jaap de Visser, *Local Government Law of South Africa* (LexisNexis 2009) 1-3 to 1-9.

⁴ Tinashe C Chigwata, Jaap de Visser and Lungelwa Kaywood, ‘Introduction’ in Tinashe C Chigwata, Jaap de Visser and Lungelwa Kaywood (eds), *The Journey to Transform Local Government* (Juta 2019) 1.

⁵ See Patricia Ntliziywana, ‘Professionalisation of Local Government in South Africa’ in Tinashe C Chigwata, Jaap de Visser and Lungelwa Kaywood (eds), *The Journey to Transform Local Government* (Juta 2019) 59.

economies has not made the situation any better. South Africa's GDP is estimated to grow by merely 1.5, 1.7 and 2.1 per cent in 2019, 2020 and 2021, respectively.⁶ The unemployment rate, which in the second quarter of 2019 stood at 29 per cent, is another indicator of an economy in trouble.⁷ It is thus without doubt that the economy is failing to generate sufficient resources, at a faster rate, for the state to cater for the needs of its estimated 58.78 million population (mid 2019 estimate).⁸ This partially explains why poverty remains widespread, inequalities continue to deepen and universal access to basic services remains a dream for many South Africans.

The citizens have been impatient with the ANC government's performance in the last few years.⁹ The political dominance of the ANC, reflected by, among other things, its two-thirds majority in the National Assembly in the early years of the democratic era, has slowly been eroded. In the 2019 elections, the ruling party won by 56 per cent of the national vote and narrowly won Gauteng province while the opposition, Democratic Alliance, kept its majority in the Western Cape province. At local government level, after the 2016 local government elections, the ruling party is no longer in control of four key metropolitan municipalities. Of the four, one is the legislative capital (City of Cape Town), the other is the administrative capital (Tshwane) while the City of Johannesburg is the economic hub of the country. Some form of coalition governments were formed in Johannesburg, Tshwane and Nelson Mandela Bay following the failure by any of the political parties to acquire a majority in these municipalities.

The metropolitan regions and cities remain key attraction points for people from rural areas in search for better economic opportunities. By 2017, over 67 per cent of the total population of South Africa was already residing in urban areas, including cities.¹⁰ Consequently, rural areas have been left with a thin base to tap resources such as skilled manpower, a development which undermines their capacity to deliver. On the other hand, the infrastructure in these metropolitan areas is overwhelmed by the large-scale inward emigration and is failing to cope, as a result. For instance, a significant number of the population in these metropolitan regions still resides in informal settlements with no or limited access to basic public services. Even if such services were to be provided, a large portion of people in these areas are not able to pay due to incapacity. Thus, local government, which is positioned at the heart of state public service delivery in South Africa,¹¹ continues to face a variety of challenges, which are both within and outside of its control.

⁶ National Treasury, 'Municipal Budget Circular for the 2019/20 MTREF' (MFMA Circular no 94, Municipal Finance Management Act No 56 of 2003, May 2019) 2.

⁷ Statistics South Africa (2019) <<http://www.statssa.gov.za/>> accessed 30 July 2019.

⁸ *ibid.*

⁹ See Ntliziywana, 'Professionalisation of Local Government in South Africa', above, 59, 61, 63.

¹⁰ See Statista, 'South Africa: Urbanization from 2009 to 2019' (*Statista*, 2020) <<https://www.statista.com/statistics/455931/urbanization-in-south-africa/>> accessed 9 December 2019.

¹¹ See Steytler and De Visser, *Local Government Law of South Africa*, above, 1-3.

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